

David Luke, Professor in Practice and Strategic Director at the Firoz Lalji Institute for Africa, London School of Economics and Political Science

Knowledge without boundaries

– David Luke

Publishing books open access enables academics to broaden the reach of their work, inform global debate and help shape policy.

David Luke wants his research to have impact and make a difference. To achieve that, the Professor in Practice and Strategic Director at the Firoz Lalji Institute for Africa at the London School of Economics and Political Science says research needs to get into the hands of people who need it and can use it. Publishing open access enables him to do that.

Sharing Knowledge

Luke thinks it is critically important that people across the globe have equal access to knowledge. He said:

“ I think research should be shared among scholars, among people who can use the research. I think being able to share research across boundaries is a great thing. It’s how knowledge can make a difference.

There is one audience in particular that Luke wants to reach with his research – an African audience. His latest book, published with LSE Press, is called How Africa

Trades. He knows from experience how hard it is to get books and research to libraries and people who need it in Africa. He also knows what a difference it would make if that access barrier was removed.

Research as a lever for change

Anyone who is working to bring about change – policy makers, scholars, community groups and activists, for example – need access to insights, ideas and information as they emerge. Luke and his team of researchers have just finished a new book, called *How Africa Eats*. It too will be published open access and Luke hopes it will help drive change.

He explained:

“We are hoping this book will revive thinking about the urgency of dealing with problems of hunger. We thought new research could uncover where the bottlenecks are and give policy makers, activists and other people, new material for campaigning.”

Challenging assumptions

Luke says it is also important that new research is circulated in the Global North, to reframe the debate and stimulate thinking around current challenges and opportunities in Africa.

He said:

“Some of this work challenges assumptions in the Global North, so it’s also aimed at scholars, policy makers and others in the Global North.”

Benefits to academics

Publishing open access has had a positive impact on the careers of Luke and his co-authors, giving them and their work greater visibility. *How Africa Trades* won the BCA (Business Council for Africa) African Business Book of the Year Award 2024, with judges praising the fact the book was accessible, due to being open access. Luke has been invited to various events, including a visit to the Carnegie Endowment for International Peace in the US. And two of the researchers in his team have gone on to secure new, permanent posts.

Luke says having published open access also helps when reaching out for funding. Foundation and funding bodies like the fact the team have and continue to publish open access, that the research reaches a wide audience and is breaking down access barriers.

The future of publishing

Luke firmly believes that the academic community will embrace open access and that the funding costs will be built into grants. In Luke's case, the costs of publishing his books open access were waived because he is a researcher at LSE.

He said:

"This is the direction of travel. It's just a matter of time."